

MANAGEMENT OF THE COMPETITIVENESS OF WHOLESALE AND RETAIL TRADE ENTERPRISES

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Annotation The article deals with the issues of competitiveness of wholesale and retail trade enterprises, the factors affecting the competitiveness of wholesale and retail trade enterprises, as well as the problems of formation of competitiveness, competitive the benefits of retailers in a transforming economy..

Key words: enterprise competitiveness, factors of enterprise efficiency competitiveness.

Theoretical aspects of the essence of the competitiveness of an enterprise are reflected in the scientific works of domestic and foreign scientists: I. Ansof, P. Drucker, H. Mackle, M. Meskon, M. Porter, A. Smith, D. Ricardo, N.A. Savelyeva, R.A. Fatkhutdinova, G.P. Kotikova, Rakhimova R.K., Rakhimova A.A., S. Ogorodova, E. Kozlova and others.

The study of factors affecting competitiveness is devoted to works by M. Porter, N.S. Yashchina, I.M. Smoleichuk, N.M. Miloserdova, Sh.A. Solieva, Radzhabova R.K., K.A. Raitsky and others.

However, the problems of formation of competitiveness, competitive the benefits of retailers in a transforming economics have not been fully studied. Some aspects of these problems in the service sector are disclosed in the works of such scientists I. Aminov, A.A. Isokov, I.A. Zhebelev, M. Gelvanovsky, S.J. Komilov, Ya.V. Trofimova, Kh.N. Fakerova, S. Khabibova, N. Sanginova, V.P. Gruzina, M. Jamshedova, F.R. Sharopova, K. Yashin, E.N. Yalunina, etc. The above scientists, as well as the results obtained as a result of research, have made a significant contribution to the development of the theory of competition, the competitiveness of enterprises. At the same time, it should be noted that the specific features of the formation and management of the competitiveness of retail trade enterprises have not been sufficiently studied and require further scientific reflection, and therefore, the expansion of work in this area is an urgent scientific and practical task, which justifies the choice and significance of the research topic. An analysis of the works of domestic and foreign scientists shows that in there is no consensus in the economic literature on the definition "competition", "competitiveness". These categories are mainly considered at the level of the economy of the country, its regions, and not enough attention is paid to competitiveness at the enterprise level, in particular, retail trade.

The main role in ensuring the competitiveness of the enterprise is assigned to competitive advantages. At the same time, this category should be considered at various levels, both in a broader and narrower sense, which allows for the relationship between them.

The above definitions characterize the "competitiveness of an enterprise" as a fixed (constant) value, not taking into account that the competitiveness of an economic entity in different periods of time can change under the influence of various factors. The basic basis on which the competitiveness of an enterprise is formed is the economic potential, which is

formed under the influence of various factors in the driving force of development - the competitive position of the enterprise.

The competitive position of an enterprise is a set of competitive advantages that provide the most favorable position for it in a certain competitive segment of the economy. A stable, sustainable competitive position allows for sustainable enterprise competitiveness.

Under the current conditions, management issues are of particular importance. Competitiveness of retail enterprises, which is understood as a set of measures aimed at optimizing the economic mechanism for the formation of competitive advantages of its subjects. The competitiveness of an enterprise is largely determined by the level the competitiveness of its goods and services, along with indicators characterizing the efficiency of the enterprise itself. Based on this, the internal factors of competitiveness of retail enterprises are considered by the author in two directions:

- 1) factors of competitiveness of retail services;
- 2) factors of competitiveness associated with the activities of the enterprise itself.

Analysis of domestic and foreign sources on assessment approaches social and economic efficiency of trade enterprises showed that, in At present, resource and cost approaches are used to the greatest extent, in which general and particular performance indicators are calculated. According to leading economists, when evaluating the effectiveness of retail enterprises, it is advisable to use a resource approach, while giving preference to the implementation of goals that characterize the stability of the company's market position and the implementation of marketing principles and the achievement of optimal strategic guidelines.

The turnover of retailers is one of the main indicators economic and social development of the country and regions. This indicator reflects the processes taking place in the volume and structure of consumption of material goods. Therefore, to a certain extent, it characterizes the standard of living of the population.

Assessment of the competitive environment in the food market goods, should be considered the most important process of a comprehensive study of the state of retail trade, tk. it allows you to fully determine the position of a retail trade enterprise among competitors, determine the development trend of the market of competitors and the most "dangerous" competitors in it.

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